

The Potential of Distributed Acoustic Sensing for Seismological Monitoring (Appendix)

Emanuele Bozzi

Abstract

This document contains the appendix files of the PhD Thesis: *The Potential of Distributed Acoustic Sensing for Seismological Monitoring*. The author, myself, is a PhD candidate at the University of Milano-Bicocca.

1 Abroad Period at ETH-Zurich

ETH Zurich, specifically the "Seismology and Wave Physics" group within the Institute of Geophysics <https://cos.ethz.ch/research.html>, is actively conducting research on DAS and its applications in seismology. This group, which I visited for an eight-month period during my PhD, focuses primarily on theoretical studies about the wave propagation in complex media and the modeling of full seismic wavefields, including strain/strain-rate, as well as data acquisition and processing.

The activities I did during my stay there can be sum-up with the following list:

- Test a package, called *Pyber*, for full-waveform (strain/strain-rate) simulation (Afanasiev et al., 2019) of a well-known event recorded by a DAS deployment and check it with observed data;
- Test standard and not-standard (e.g., phase weighted stack) data processing techniques to enhance SNRs of seismic events;
- Comparison of a coherence-based picker (Klaasen et al., 2023) and a more standard STA/LTA based picker (Baer et al., 1987);
- Estimation of differential arrival times from cross-correlation of DAS channel couples and comparison with absolute arrival times;
- Familiarization with the concept of a Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (HMC) algorithm (Gebraad et al., 2020), which exploits the local misfit gradient during model space exploration. Then, test it with P-wave arrival and differential times for event location;
- Test data selection for event location purposes, both arrival and differential times;
- Test a Julia package to compute traveltimes in complex media, employing the fast-marching method (Zunino et al., 2023) e eventually expanded for

event location purposes with the adjoint methods.

The following appendices refers to relevant results obtained during the abroad period a ETH, both merged and not-merged with published conference abstracts, manuscripts or scientific articles.

1.1 Full-waveform Simulation with Pyber

This test investigates the complexities of observed arrival times using advanced full-waveform modeling.

The results indicate that the Pyber package, which computes strain and strain-rate wavefields for a given geometry while accounting for DAS axial sensitivity, struggles to capture the full complexity of the observed data. The discrepancies are likely due to more intricate features not strictly related to geometry, such as cable coupling or site effects. Given the nature of the event, a volcano-tectonic earthquake, and the use of a telecommunication cable sensed with DAS, both factors are plausible explanations.

With DAS we can record earthquakes ... with an amazing spatial density

Signal amplitudes may vary (a lot) along the array

The azimuthal directions spanned by the array are very limited.

SNR variations: Coupling? Local velocity anomalies?

Standard automatic P-wave arrival time retrieval... messy

The picker: Baer and Kradolfer, 1987, a variant of STA/LTA on a submarine cable (NESTOR).

Observation: Phase mispick, especially in low SNR sections

How to manage data uncertainties?

Picks distribution

Automatic P-wave arrival times statistics >> complex

Synthetic waveforms

Full waveform strain-rate simulation with Pyber (axial sensitivity is taken into account) and comparison with observed data

Observation: Synthetic simulations fail in sufficiently reproducing the complexity of the observed waveform, especially the P-coda. Most likely both cable coupling and site effects account for this discrepancy.

Complex P-coda >>
scattered automatic
P-wave arrival times

1.2 Coherence-based and Standard Picker Comparison

Here, I compare a standard 1D automatic picker, based on the energy content of the signal (Baer et al., 1987), with a coherence-based picker that exploits the local coherence of the P-wave waveform (Klaasen et al., 2023). The results show highly scattered P-wave arrival times for the standard picker and a limited ability to pick along the entire cable, likely due to its sensitivity to local SNR variations (e.g., coupling). Additionally, it suffers from evident phase mispicks between P- and S- waves. The coherence-based picking algorithm has similar moveouts compared to the standard picker, indicating that it picks the same phase, at least the P phase, and it lacks scattering due to its design. However, it fails to work for a few events.

When inverting the P-wave arrival times estimated with these two algorithms, using the same HMC algorithm (Zunino et al., 2023), discrepancies in the locations are evident. This confirms that the arrival time statistics for data-intensive technologies such as DAS affect both the precision and accuracy of the locations.

Standard picker vs cross-correlation and interpolation-based picker

Comparison of P-wave arrival times estimates for a set of events

Event location

Grímsvötn experiment: a DAS array in Iceland to monitor volcano-tectonic seismicity in a caldera.

Using P-wave arrival times to estimate the event location, same HMC algorithm

Observation:

Event locations differs evidently, as expected, give the different data scattering and estimated wavefront moveout. This confirms how the choice of the picker strongly affects the estimations of the source parameters in complex DAS data.

1.3 HMC and P-wave Differential Times

The Hamiltonian Monte Carlo method has also been used to invert P-wave differential times. Compared to standard Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC), it mimics a physical system (hence the name Hamiltonian) to accelerate exploration in model space toward regions of high PPD, exploiting the gradient of the misfit function. Here, I compare the inversion of P-wave arrival times with selected differential times for event location using the same event. The selection helps to decimate the data space and avoids using unmeaningful differential times, specifically those corresponding to poorly correlated channels ($MCC < 0.5$) and those that are more than 100 m apart (> 100 m). The use of differential times provides a more accurate event location in terms of azimuth.

The results of this test have been also presented at GNGTS 2024 conference.

Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) arrays provide dense sampling of the strain wavefield

- DAS usually provides 100s up to 1000s measurement points (**dense spatial sampling**);
- However, the estimation of absolute phase arrival times are prone to local and intrinsic noise sources (reducing the number of meaningful data points) >> Effects on data inversion (e.g., location uncertainty);
- Nevertheless, DAS is ideal to exploit the redundant information provided by **time delays between DAS channels** as a data space to be inverted for event location;
- **Thus, here we test an Hamiltonian Monte Carlo method (uncertainty quantification!) with differential arrival times, to look for event location performances**

Data space: differential arrival times

TEST: We invert both absolute arrival times and differential arrival times to compare location uncertainties . The solution is not provided as a single value but a probability distribution (combination of Prior + Likelihood, Bayesian approach)

1. We want to converge faster to the peak and, hence, provide a better picture of the PPD (regions of higher posterior probability)

Posterior Probability Distribution (PPD)
(e.g., event's latitude, longitude)

2. The proposed parameters are treated as "particles" exploring the "posterior probability function topography" (**potential energy**), provided by auxiliary momenta variables (**kinetic energy**). Numerical integration (leapfrog method) is used to simulate particle dynamics (Hamiltonian system). The new proposed Hamiltonian state is accepted according to Metropolis criterion.

Getting some intuition of the Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (HMC) method

Compared to a more standard Markov Chain Monte Carlo approach, the misfit gradient is exploited to approximate PPDs.

HMC takes inspiration from hamiltonian dynamics (describing motion of particles) > *set of parameters = particle moving (potential + kinetic energy)*.

HMC is ideal for high-dimensional problems.

HMC algorithm to locate seismic events with differential arrival times

Locating quakes on Grimsvötn, Iceland

- We started from the Hamiltonian Monte Carlo (Zunino et al., 2023) code, originally developed for P-wave absolute arrival times, and modified it to deal with P-wave differential arrival times (check **HMCLab!**);
- We estimated time delays cross-correlating filtered P wave onsets. Then we **selected differential arrival times** based on two thresholds: **minimum cross-correlation index** and **maximum interchannel distance** to use meaningful delay times;
- **Two well-known events** are exploited as a “safe” environment to test the algorithm and comparing location uncertainties (absolute and differential arrival times).

Applications to well-known case studies: Azuma Volcano (Japan)

The volcanic event location is known from a local network of nodes and previous seismicity clustering in the same area.

Results: Azuma Volcano

Please note that the density distributions are different, given the amount of explored models (500.000 vs 1000). Nevertheless, less proposals are needed with differential arrival times. Vp velocity (4000 m/s) and x,y,x prior ranges are fixed for both inversions.

Differential arrival times provide a better constrain on the known directionality (NW) of the source

1.4 Test Data Selection for Event Location (P-wave Arrival Times)

Data selection has already been tested on differential times to avoid inverting unmeaningful data. This approach has also been applied to P-wave arrival times, resulting in more accurate event locations. In this case, the criterion for selecting data is based on the distance from the event, ensuring that only data from closer channels are used. Thus, this test further confirms the need for data selection with DAS to avoid inverting outliers, if the same importance is given to all data.

DATA SELECTION ON P-WAVE ARRIVAL TIMES

Data outliers affect the accuracy of event locations.

A possible mitigation to the problem is the “expert” selection of arrival times.

Here, I select DAS channels (and thus P-wave arrival times) closer to the event.

BEFORE
(no selection)

2 Field Experiences

During the PhD project, I had the opportunity to participate in a seismological monitoring campaign in a geothermal field in Tuscany, Italy. In this context, I assisted with the preliminary tests for the installation of a fiber optic cable (FOC) and subsequently with the installation in the field. Additionally, towards the end of the project, I was involved in testing two novel DAS interrogators at the INGV research center in Pisa, Italy.

I here report some photos of the two experiences.

2.1 DAS for seismological monitoring, first test, Lagoni Rossi (Italy), March 2022

2.2 Test of two novel DAS interrogators, INGV-PI, Pisa (Italy), May 2024)

Figure 1: Trench excavated to bury the FOC

Figure 2: Laser interrogator used to sense the cable

Figure 3: DAS interrogators

Figure 4: Laboratory test to record a simplified seismic wavefield

Figure 5: Selected garden for a ground test

3 Talks

During my two visiting periods at ETH Zurich, Institute of Geophysics, Seismology and Wave Physics (SWP) group, and at ICM in Barcelona, I was invited to give talks about the research activities I was involved in. Here, I present the first slide from each seminar. Most of the issues addressed in these talks have been collected in scientific papers or conference abstracts.

Additionally, I was recently invited by a seismological research centre, the Centro di Ricerche Sismologiche (CRS), part of the Istituto Nazionale di Oceanografia e Geofisica Sperimentale (OGS), to give a talk on the opportunities and limitations of DAS for seismological monitoring.

3.1 Internal seminar SWP Group, ETH Zurich, Zurich (Switzerland), October 2023

Earthquake location with DAS traveltime data

A PhD project funded by INGV in collaboration with University of Milano-Bicocca.

Goal : *exploring DAS potential for seismic monitoring*

Emanuele Bozzi, PhD student, University of Milano-Bicocca, Milan, Italy

ETH zürich

—SWP—

ISTITUTO NAZIONALE
DI GEOFISICA E VULCANOLOGIA

ETH Zurich, Department of Earth Science
October 19th, 2023

**3.2 Institut de Ciències del Mar (ICM), Barcelona (Spain),
March 2024**

CANDAS-2

(Automatic pickers and location uncertainty comparison)

3.3 OGS seminar, Udine (Italy), May 2024

DAS Technology for Seismological Monitoring Using Fiber Optics: Exploring **Possibilities** and **Limitations**

Emanuele Bozzi

Phd Candidate | University of Milano-Bicocca

Centro Ricerche Sismologiche (CRS)
Udine | May 28th, 2024

4 Conference Abstracts

I here report the conference abstract for which I was a first author during the PhD project.

4.1 Gruppo Nazionale Geofisica Terra Solida (GNGTS), Bologna (Italy), February 2023

Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) data for seismic monitoring: influence of cable geometry and installation context

E. Bozzi¹, N. Piana Agostinetti¹, G. Saccorotti², A. F. Baird³, C. Becerril⁴, B. Biondi⁵, A. Fichtner⁶, S. Klaasen⁶, N. Lindsey⁷, T. Nishimura⁸, J. Shen⁹, A. Ugalde¹⁰, F. Walter¹¹, S. Yuan⁵, T. Zhu⁹

¹ *University of Milano-Bicocca, Milano, Italy.*

² *Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia (INGV), Pisa, Italy.*

³ *NORSAR, Kjeller, Norway*

⁴ *Université Côte d'Azur, CNRS, Observatoire de la Côte d'Azur, IRD, Géoazur, Valbonne, France*

⁵ *Stanford University, Stanford, California, USA*

⁶ *ETH Zürich, Zürich, Switzerland*

⁷ *FiberSense™*

⁸ *Tohoku University, Tohoku, Japan*

⁹ *PennState University, State College, Pennsylvania, USA*

¹⁰ *Barcelona Center for Subsurface Imaging, Barcelona, Spain*

¹¹ *Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research WSL, Uitikon, Switzerland*

Introduction

Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) technology exploits laser interrogation of fiber optic cables (FOCs) to retrieve a very-dense array of longitudinal strain/strain-rate sensors (Zhan, 2020). DAS detects phase changes in the backscattered energy from natural fiber inhomogeneities. Raw optical measurements are integrated along a discrete cable portion, called “gauge length” and then related to local strain/strain-rate at each “DAS channel”. DAS can record external inputs deforming FOCs in a broadband frequency range (Paitz et al., 2021), with a maximum interrogation range around 100 km (Landrø et al., 2021).

DAS is a promising research field for seismology. Indeed, it allows for unprecedented wavefield spatial sampling (up to < 1 m) and potential ubiquitous monitoring, especially when pre-existing telecommunication optical fibers are interrogated (Lindsey & Martin, 2021). As a matter of fact, it can map subsurface heterogeneities (Jousset et al., 2018; Lindsey et al., 2020; Lior et al., 2022, Yuan et al., 2020), monitor natural (Lindsey et al., 2017; Biondi et al., 2017; Ugalde et al., 2022) or induced seismicity (Karrenbach et al., 2019), especially in geothermal fields (Lellouch et al., 2020; Obermann et al., 2018), implement fast response to study aftershock sequences (Li et al., 2021), characterize natural seismicity induced by glacier movements (Walter et al., 2020) and urban noise (Biondi et al., 2022; Shen and Zhu, 2021). However, DAS data is usually affected by lower

signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) compared to standard seismic sensors (Li & Zhan, 2018; Walter et al., 2020). Moreover, signal incoherencies are common, due to site effects and poor ground-fiber coupling (Van den Ende & Ampuero, 2021).

This work focuses on the potential of DAS for seismological monitoring. Standard seismic arrays are usually evaluated on (a) their geometry and (b) the SNR of the recorded events. The potential of DAS arrays instead, is conditioned by the following factors: a) the signal directivity, i.e. the strain/strain-rate are measured only for their longitudinal components along the fiber direction; b) the differences in FOC coupling with the ground, and c) the higher susceptibility to local rock elasticity variations (Ajo-Franklin et al., 2019; Van den Ende & Ampuero, 2021). Indeed, all these factors affect the signal amplitudes and their spatial coherence. Therefore, arrival times estimated on DAS data show complex noise characteristics, which in turn might influence the uncertainty of the event locations.

FOCs are the backbone of the global telecommunication network and show a worldwide distribution (e.g., urban, ocean seafloor environments). Despite various successful case-studies (Fichtner et al., 2022; Jousset et al., 2018; Klaasen et al., 2021; Lellouch et al., 2020; Lindsey et al., 2017; Nishimura et al., 2021; Van den Ende & Ampuero, 2021; Walter et al., 2020; Zhu & Stensrud, 2019), a more general exploration on the influence of geometry and installation environment on their seismic monitoring potential is still lacking. Therefore, in this work, DAS is tested for an operative monitoring task, investigating the influence of different sources of noise in events' arrival times estimated with DAS and exploiting an unprecedentedly various database, including different typologies of seismic events (earthquakes, ice-quakes, volcanic earthquakes) in numerous installation contexts.

Data and methods

Diversified DAS datasets have been collected from online open access databases and from direct agreements with researchers responsible for the specific acquisitions. Both telecommunication cables, repurposed for DAS monitoring tasks, and suited installations, are included in the study (Figure 1). Each DAS dataset is provided with the recording of at least a local seismic event (< 100 km from the array barycenter). A reference event is then selected for the study and an independent location is provided, from the analysis of seismological catalogs or "expert" analysis of local seismic arrays/selected DAS channels. A basic pre-processing is adopted to increase the SNRs of the recorded events, including linear de-trending, cosine tapering and bandpass filtering. Moreover, spatial subsampling is embraced when the DAS gauge length exceeds the channel spacing. This procedure can help increase the SNRs (Piana Agostinetti et al., 2022), especially in poorly coupled FOCs portions. A coherent automatic picking procedure (Baer & Kradolfer, 1987) is adopted to pick the first onsets at the DAS channels of each pre-processed event. Then, a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) approach is used for estimating hypocentral parameters (Riva and Piana Agostinetti, 2022).

Beside the estimated locations, based on observed arrival times, four synthetic tests are implemented to simulate different sources of noise in DAS arrival times and to measure how such

noise sources affect the location accuracies . (1) The first test (SYNTH-01) consists of the inversion of synthetic traveltimes computed on the DAS channels, assuming the independent location as the “true” one and adding white Gaussian noise. This exercise provides insight into the geometrical effects that influence the precision of epicentral location. In addition to this, some geometric parameters are computed to better describe the geometry of the problem in function of the location uncertainties. Then, 2) three different statistical assumptions are considered for such traveltimes, to simulate typical observations in DAS recordings, that is: i) the arrival time picking uncertainty increases with the distance from channel to the event (SYNTH-02), ii) S-wave pickings are mis-labeled as P-waves at some DAS channels (SYNTH-03) and iii) specific channel packets are associated with very-low SNRs (as a tentative to model fiber coupling inhomogeneities (SYNTH-04)). Finally, these synthetic traveltimes are inverted to assess the influence of these assumptions on the ultimate outcome of the monitoring exercise: event location.

Results

The estimated epicentral locations obtained from the automatic traveltime picking procedure exhibit varying degrees of uncertainty. DAS arrays with greater azimuthal coverage provide more consistent locations (Fig 2a), which is an expected behavior, particularly considering the longitudinal polarization of strain/strain-rate measurements. This behavior is further supported by SYNTH-01 test (Fig 2b). Furthermore, the azimuthal gap parameter influences the epicentral uncertainty when compared to the independent location . However, exceptions to this behavior are common, indicating that geometrical factors alone do not exclusively control the uncertainties in source location with DAS. Such “biases” between observed and reference locations are indeed partially explained by arrival time uncertainties, especially the ones modeled by SYNTH-03 and SYNTH-04. As an example, Figures 2c-d show how the observed location uncertainty can be reproduced, to a certain degree, from synthetic simulations.

Figure 1. DAS array geometries. Three categories are identified: 1) oceanic telecommunication cables, which represent FOCs installed in continental shelf or continental shelf-oceanic floor transition environments (names: HCMR, MONTEREY, NESTOR, MEUST, CANARY); 2) terrestrial telecommunication cables, which represent FOCs installed in sub-aerial environments (names: STANFORD-1, AZUMA-VOLCANO, FORESEE, STANFORD-2, HENGILL-GFZ, HENGILL-NORSAR) and 3) "fit-for-purpose" cables, which represent FOCs installed for scientific studies (names: MOUNT-MEAGER, RHONEGLETSCHER-GLACIER, POROTOMO, GRÍMSVÖTN).

Figure 2. DAS epicentral locations and their uncertainties compared with independent locations. Orange dots are used to plot the samples from the posterior probability density (PPDs) functions, while orange stars represent the mean solutions and red stars the independent locations. A) The event location obtained from automatic arrival time picking reproduces satisfactorily the reference one, for the event recorded by GRÍMSVÖTN, given the low epicentral gap. B) SYNTH-01 test for NESTOR DAS array shows a high longitudinal uncertainty, given the quasi-linear north-south geometry. C) SYNTH-04 test for RHONEGLETSCHER array shows that, if coupling effects on traveltimes are considered, the synthetic location can partially reconstruct the D) calculated location.

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Reference author: Emanuele Bozzi - e.bozzi3@campus.unimib.it

**4.2 European Geoscience Union (EGU), Vienna (Austria),
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EGU General Assembly 2023

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Effects of cable geometry and specific noise sources on DAS monitoring potential

Emanuele Bozzi et al. [▶](#)

The Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) method re-purposes fiber optic cables into a very-dense array of strain/strain-rate sensors, capable of detecting different types of seismic events. However, DAS data are characterized by lower SNRs compared with standard seismic sensors, mainly because of a) strong directivity effects, 2) ground coupling inhomogeneities, and 3) site effects. Hence, beyond the array geometry, specific noise sources may reduce the potential of DAS for seismic monitoring. Previous research has already shown successful case-studies for event detection/location. Nevertheless, a coherent test on the performances of various arrays of different sizes and geometries is still lacking.

In this study, an extensive DAS database is organized for such a goal, including 15 DAS arrays that recorded at least one seismic event (located at a range of distances from the arrays). P wave arrival times are exploited to estimate the epicentral parameters with a Markov Chain Monte Carlo method. Then, to analyze the effects of cable geometry and potential sources of noise/ambiguity on the location uncertainties, a series of synthetic tests are performed, where synthetic traveltimes are modified as follows: a) adding noise with equal variance to all the DAS channels (SYNTH-01), b) adding noise characterized by an increasing variance with the distance from the event (SYNTH-02), c) simulating the mis-pick between P and S phases (SYNTH-03) and d) adding noise with a variance influenced by cable coupling inhomogeneities (SYNTH-04). Results show that the epicentral locations with automatic P wave arrival times have different degrees of uncertainty, given the geometrical relation between the event and the DAS arrays. This behavior is confirmed by the SYNTH-01 test, indicating that specific geometries provide a lower constraint on event location. Moreover, SYNTH-04 shows that simulating cable coupling inhomogeneities primarily reproduces the observed location uncertainties. Finally, some cases are not explained by any of the synthetic tests, stressing the possible presence of more complex noise sources contaminating the signals.

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Supplementary materials

[Supplementary material file](#)

4.3 GNGTS, Ferrara (Italy), February 2024

Differential arrival times for event location with DAS data

E. Bozzi ¹

L. Gebraad ²

A. Fichtner ³

N. Piana Agostinetti ¹

G. Saccorotti ⁴

T. Kiers ³

T. Nishimura ⁵

¹ *University of Milano-Bicocca (Milan, Italy)*

² *Mondaic Ltd (Zurich, Switzerland)*

³ *ETH Zurich, Institute of Geophysics (Zurich, Switzerland)*

⁴ *Instituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia (Pisa, Italy)*

⁵ *Tohoku University, Department of Geophysics (Tohoku, Japan)*

Standard seismic networks typically use absolute arrival times of specific seismic phases to estimate source locations. In this context, multiple sensors are positioned over a monitored area, aiming to minimize the azimuthal gap to known seismicity clusters. Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) technology, which converts fiber optic cables (FOCs) into very dense seismic arrays, is nowadays used for similar purposes. DAS has the additional advantage of being able to exploit preexisting telecommunication FOCs (Telecom-FOCs). However, since the original installation purpose for Telecom-FOCs doesn't align with seismological needs, the spanned azimuthal directions can be limited. Hence, relying on absolute arrival times for event location might result in uncertain locations, given poor waveform moveouts and site-specific sources of noise in the data. Nevertheless, the intrinsic DAS channels' spatial density provide a good opportunity to test multi-channel cross-correlation techniques. Here, to assess the potential benefit from using differential arrival times for event location, we cross-correlate all possible DAS channel pairs and identify P-wave time delays. We focus on well-known test environments (i.e., known event locations) and

use a Hamiltonian Monte Carlo algorithm to estimate hypocentral parameter uncertainties, considering both absolute and differential arrival times. We demonstrate how differential arrival times better constrain the events' azimuthal directions compared to absolute arrival times. However, computational costs are inevitably higher due to the significant increase in data points when considering all the P-wave delays. A mitigation to this issue is reached by selecting measurements based on thresholds for the minimum cross-correlation index and maximum interchannel distance. This work illustrates how to potentially alleviate DAS geometrical limitations on event location by exploiting selected differential arrival times.

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Differential arrival times for source location with DAS arrays: tests on data selection and automatic weighting procedure

Emanuele Bozzi¹, Nicola Piana Agostinetti¹, Gilberto Saccorotti², Andreas Fichtner³, Lars Gebraad^{3,4}, Tjeerd Kiers³, and Takeshi Nishimura⁵

¹University of Milano Bicocca, Environmental and Earth Sciences Department (DISAT), Milan, Italy
(e.bozzi3@campus.unimib.it)

²Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia (INGV), Pisa, Italy

³ETH Zürich, Department of Earth Sciences, Institute of Geophysics, Zürich, Switzerland

⁴Mondaic AG, Zürich, Switzerland

⁵Tohoku University, Department of Geophysics, Tohoku, Japan

Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) technology is currently used to monitor seismic activity, offering a unique spatially-dense representation of the along-the-cable strain wavefield. Traditional seismic networks typically rely on the timing of specific seismic phases to estimate source locations. In this context, DAS arrays may fail to provide accurate traveltimes because of spatially-heterogeneous waveforms. The motivations are (but not limited to) the directional sensitivity, the heterogeneous cable ground-coupling and the enhanced sensitivity to lateral variations in the medium elastic properties. The resulting fluctuations in signal-to-noise ratios of the dense DAS channels pose significant challenges in the automatic picking of body phases, e.g., P-wave Absolute Arrival Times (P-ARTs). Consequently, the complex distribution of the estimated traveltimes impacts the accuracy of event locations, especially if incorrect assumptions on error statistics (e.g., Normal distribution) are considered. In this study, we address this issue by exploiting the intrinsic DAS measurements' spatial density and testing selected P-wave Differential Arrival Times (P-DATs) for source location. We estimate P-DATs for all the possible DAS channel pairs by identifying the time delay corresponding to the peak of each cross-correlation function. Subsequently, we select P-DATs based on two criteria: interchannel distance and cross-correlation index value. This procedure is often employed to reduce the risk of mixing delay times from coherent and incoherent waveforms. As a first test, using a probabilistic inversion (Hamiltonian Monte Carlo method), we demonstrate how the selected P-DATs provide a better constraint on the event's azimuthal direction compared to P-ARTs. Then, as a second experiment, we move from a subjective selection of P-DATs. To do so, we test a fully-automated and data-driven covariance matrix weighting procedure, in a probabilistic inversion scheme. Specifically, we compute posterior probability distributions for both the physical parameters (event location) and hyperparameters related to data features (interchannel distance and cross-correlation index thresholds). In this scheme, the hyperparameters define each weight along the diagonal of the covariance matrix. These tests offer useful insights into the utilization of P-DATs for event location with DAS. Moreover, we provide an automatic approach to avoid subjective biases based on

preconceptions in the a-priori data selection.

**4.5 Fiber Optic Sensing in Geosciences (FOSG), Catania
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Comparing location uncertainties with automatic pickers on DAS data: case studies from Canary Islands

Emanuele Bozzi¹, Nicola Piana Agostinetti¹, Arantza Ugalde², Hugo Latorre², Melania Cubas Armas², Sergi Ventosa², Antonio Villaseñor², and Gilberto Saccorotti³

¹University of Milano Bicocca, Environmental and Earth Sciences Department (DISAT), Milan (Italy)

²Institute of Marine Sciences – CSIC, Barcelona (Spain)

³Istituto Nazionale di Geofisica e Vulcanologia, Pisa (Italy)

Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) offers unprecedented meter-scale spatial sampling of strain/strain-rate wavefields, enabling unaliased seismic event observations. DAS technology utilizes fiber optic cables (FOCs), extending seismological observations to extreme environments, including ocean floors. Given the logistical difficulties in deploying and maintaining traditional seismic stations in these contexts, seismological data near oceanic earthquake sources remain limited. On a positive note, telecommunication FOCs are often deployed on the ocean bottoms to connect urban areas on land, potentially bridging this observational gap.

Traditional seismological monitoring, which aims to locate earthquake sources, typically relies on phase picking and subsequent data inversion. In a standard seismometer network, automatically-retrieved arrival times can be manually validated by expert operators; however, this task becomes practically impossible with DAS due to the unprecedented data density it offers, which can easily reach tens of thousands channels, considering the current capabilities of interrogating cables up to 100 km. For the purpose of leveraging both data measurements close to the source (DAS) and the improved azimuthal coverage by land stations, DAS data flows must be automated. Potential solutions include accurately tuning automatic pickers for the specific FOC and/or employing data selection and weighing procedures. Recently, pickers based on machine learning have been tested for DAS as substitutes for standard pickers, offering promising results and efficient arrival time measurements. Despite these advancements, challenges persist in accurately estimating onsets due to spatial variability in DAS waveforms, arising from a) uniaxial signal polarization, b) sensitivity to site conditions, and c) heterogeneities in FOC coupling. These data uncertainties, in turn, affect event location accuracy.

We address this problem by conducting a preliminary comparison of two standard pickers (based on the actual amplitude-frequency content of each channel) with a machine-learning-derived picker. We focus on DAS recordings of six local earthquakes located on the ocean bottom between Fuerteventura and Gran Canaria islands during an experiment from November 2022 to April 2023. Each earthquake is provided with a reference location from the regional network of seismometers. Kurtosis and FilterPicker (standard pickers) and Phasenet-DAS (machine-learning picker) onsets are inverted for event location, with a focus on statistically comparing the solutions' uncertainty (scattering). To achieve this, we employed a Markov chain Monte Carlo method to estimate the Posterior Probability Densities (PPDs) of hypocentral parameters.

In a second stage, we test a data-weighting approach on absolute arrival times based on specific channel properties. The aim is to assess its effects on location PPDs, in comparison to the “not-weighted” inversion. We repurpose the same algorithm, previously used for the location comparison, to modify each entry of the covariance matrix in the Bayesian inversion scheme, thus enabling a differential weighting of the arrival times. These preliminary comparisons of the efficiency of

automatic pickers and data weighting procedures are commonly employed for the evaluation of standard seismological networks. With DAS arrays, these approaches become even more crucial, given the reduced space for manual validation by experts.

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